

Studies on Benzene-Azo-(Ethyl Acetoacetate) and Benzene-Azo-(Acetyl Acetone) as Chelating Agents

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Co-ordination complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Co(III) with benzene-azo-(ethyl acetoacetate) and benzene-azo-(acetyl acetone) have been prepared. The pyridine adducts of some of these complexes have also been prepared. The magnetic moments and the electronic absorption spectra of the complexes have been reported and discussed.

The co-ordination complexes of the versatile chelating ligands acetyl acetone and ethyl acetoacetate with transition metals are well known. But nothing is known about the complexing ability of benzene-azo-(ethyl acetoacetate)¹ (I) and benzene-azo-(acetyl acetone)² (II)

With the idea that the compounds R^IH and R^{II}H should form some interesting complexes with transition metal ions, successful attempts have been made in preparing the Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Co(III) complexes of these two ligands. From the nature of the ligands, it appears that these might behave both as bidentate as well as tridentate chelating agents.

The compounds Cu(II)R₂^I and Cu(II)R₂^{II} are sparingly soluble in ethanol but insoluble in water. These are found to be paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.94$ and 1.80 B.M.).

The electronic absorption spectra recorded in the region 200–1000 nm show absorption bands in the vicinity of 900, 780, 670, 357 and 240 nm for the compound Cu(II)R₂^I and in the vicinity of 900, 780, 670, 363 and 245 nm for Cu(II)R₂^{II}.

The last two absorption maxima i.e., in the region of 360 nm and 240 nm are also observed in case of free ligands. The log ϵ values of the absorption maxima in these two cases are always 0.3 greater in case of copper compounds than the respective free ligands. This may be regarded to support that two ligand molecules are associated with each copper atom, if these two bands are assumed to be due to ligands themselves.

1. Carl Bülow and Peter Neber, *Ber.*, 1912, **45**, 3732.

2. Erich Benary, Fritz Reiter and Helene Soenderop, *Ber.*, 1917, **50**, 65.

It is known that Cu(II) complexes have got absorption bands in the 600–900 nm region of the spectrum^{3,6,7,8,9}. In fact three d–d transitions are to be expected for Cu(II) in its complexes due to tetragonal distortion. The presence of three absorption bands near 900, 780 and 670 nm for both Cu(II)R₂^I and Cu(II)R₂^{II} in the visible spectrum can thus be accounted for. The bands at 780 nm are, however, very weakly observed and its assignment is not beyond doubt.

The nickel complexes Ni(II)R₂^I (P_y)₂ and Ni(II)R₂^{II} (P_y)₂ are paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 3.16$ B.M.) and the magnetic moment values identify these to be octahedral Ni(II) complexes³.

The U.V. and visible spectra of the complexes show the presence of absorption bands in the region 980, 800, 650, 365 and 245 nm for Ni(II)R₂^I (P_y)₂ and 960, 740, 640, 365 and 245 nm for Ni(II)R₂^{II} (P_y)₂. Most of the octahedral Ni(II) complexes exhibit charge transfer bands around 1160, 740, 650, 540 and 390 nm due to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$; ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$; ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g(D)$; ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{1g}(G)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$. Among these, the assignments of ${}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3T_{1g}(P)$ are beyond doubt according to available literature^{3,4}. However, the exact position of the bands depend upon the ligand fields.

The compound Ni(II)R₂^{II}(P_y)₂ on heating at 110°–115° for several hours lost the pyridine molecules yielding diamagnetic Ni(II)R₂^{II}. Octahedral Ni(II) complex was thus converted into a four co-ordinated planar complex³. The electronic absorption spectra of this compound in ethanolic solution show the presence of three bands in the vicinity of 540, 365 and 245 nm. Usually Ni(II) planar complexes³ have absorption band of medium intensity ($\epsilon \approx 60$) in the region of 450–600 nm.

The compound Ni(II)R₂^I (P_y)₂ did not lose the pyridine molecules even on heating at 120° for several hours.

One Co(II) complex Co(II)R₂^I (P_y)₂ isolated is found to be paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 4.89$ B.M.). From the magnetic moment value the complex may be regarded to be an octahedral one⁵.

The U.V. and visible spectra of the compound indicate the presence of bands near 940–880, 575, and 370 nm. The known transitions for the octahedral Co(II) complexes are⁴:

The ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ transition is weaker (by $\sim 10^{-2}$) than the other transitions and so it remains usually unobserved³.

3. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, 1966, p. 901, p. 882, p. 887, p. 885, and p. 871.
4. J. Lewis and R. G. Wilkins, "Modern Co-ordination Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, 1964, p. 288, p. 290, and p. 291.
5. Richard L. Carlin, "Transition metal chemistry", Vol. I, Marcel Dekker, Inc., 1965, p. 22.
6. J. Ferguson, R. L. Belford and T. S. Piper, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, **37**, 1569.
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8. J. Bjerrum, C. J. Ballhausen and C. K. Jørgensen, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1954, **8**, 1275.
9. C. K. Jørgensen, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1956, **10**, 887.

The compound $\text{Co(II)R}_2(\text{Py})_2$ on heating at 120° for several hours lost the pyridine molecules yielding paramagnetic Co(II)R_2 . ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 4.83$ B.M.). From the magnetic moment value it appears that this compound is also octahedral. The U.V. and visible spectra of the compound indicate the presence of bands near 970–880, 600, 365 and 245 nm. Thus the band positions are not seriously altered from the octahedral compound $\text{Co(II)R}_2(\text{Py})_2$. Therefore, the ligand appears to behave as a tridentate one in the compound Co(II)R_2 .

The Co(III) complexes, Co(III)R_3 and $\text{Co(III)R}^{\text{II}}_3$ both are diamagnetic. The electronic absorption spectra of these complexes are recorded in ethanolic solution. In case of Co(III)R_3 three bands around 470, 360 and 240 nm are observed. The $\log \epsilon$ values of the peaks at 360 nm and 240 nm are 0.53 greater than the respective values with the ligand $\text{R}^{\text{I}}\text{H}$. This may be interpreted that three ligand molecules are attached to each cobalt atom. These two peaks are regarded to be due to ligands themselves.

The visible absorption spectra of Co(III) complexes are expected to consist of two bands⁴ due to transitions from ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{T}_{1g}$ (475–500 nm) and ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{T}_{2g}$ (345 to 400 nm). The band at 470 nm observed may thus be attributed to the transition ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{T}_{1g}$, but nothing can be predicted regarding the band at 360 nm, because it may also be due to the ligand. The high ϵ values are mainly due to the ligand.

Four bands around 470, 370, 285 and 240 nm were observed with the compound $\text{Co(III)R}^{\text{II}}_3$. If we consider the bands at 370 and 240 nm due to the ligand, then the bands at 470 and 285 nm may be assigned to the transitions ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{T}_{1g}$ and ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{T}_{2g}$ respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation and properties of the ligands: The ligand $\text{R}^{\text{I}}\text{H}$ was prepared according to the method of Carl Bülow and Peter Neber¹ by coupling benzene diazonium chloride with ethyl acetoacetate and found m.p. 70° .

Adopting exactly similar procedure, the ligand $\text{R}^{\text{II}}\text{H}$ was prepared and found m.p. 88° . (m.p. given in literature²: 90°).

Both $\text{R}^{\text{I}}\text{H}$ and $\text{R}^{\text{II}}\text{H}$ are insoluble in water but soluble in ethanol, methanol, benzene, acetone, chloroform etc. These are also soluble in aqueous alkali solutions.

The electronic absorption spectra of the ligands $\text{R}^{\text{I}}\text{H}$ and $\text{R}^{\text{II}}\text{H}$ have been measured in speck pure ethanol. Two absorption maxima in the vicinity of 355 and 235 nm for the ligand $\text{R}^{\text{I}}\text{H}$ and 362 and 247 nm for the ligand $\text{R}^{\text{II}}\text{H}$ were observed.

Preparation of Cu(II) compounds: Copper complexes with $\text{R}^{\text{I}}\text{H}$ and $\text{R}^{\text{II}}\text{H}$ were prepared by adding an ethanolic solution of pure copper acetate ($0.0025 M$) to an ethanolic solution of ligand ($0.005 M$) and then adding NH_4OH soln. dropwise to adjust the PH between 7 and 8. Almost immediately shining micro crystals of Cu(II)R_2 were formed. These were washed with ethanol, dried in air, analysed and m.p. noted.

Preparation of Ni(II) complexes: $\text{Ni(II)R}_2(\text{Py})_2$ was prepared by dissolving freshly precipitated nickelous hydroxide in A.R. pyridine and adding to an ethanolic solution of

R^IH. Nickel solution was added in slight excess than the ratio 1 : 2. Water was added to the mixture until turbidity appeared. It was then warmed on a water bath and then allowed to stand. Greenish yellow compound separated was filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol containing a little pyridine, dried in air, analysed and m.p. noted.

Ni(II)R^{II}₂ (P_y)₂ was prepared by dissolving freshly precipitated nickelous hydroxide in pyridine and adding to an ethanolic solution of R^IH. Immediately beautiful chocolate red crystals separated. It was washed with aqueous ethanol containing a little pyridine, dried in air, analysed and m.p. noted.

Preparation of cobalt complexes : Co(II)R^I₂ (P_y)₂ was prepared by dissolving freshly precipitated cobaltous hydroxide in pyridine and adding to an ethanolic solution of R^IH. On slow evaporation of the solvent over fused calcium chloride in a desiccator, orange red compound separated. It was filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol, dried in air, analysed, and m.p. noted.

The cobaltic complexes, Co(III)R^I₃ and Co(III)R^{II}₃ were prepared by dissolving freshly precipitated cobaltous hydroxide in pyridine and adding to requisite amount of ethanolic solution of the ligand. To the mixture, an aqueous hydrogen peroxide solution was added and allowed to evaporate over fused calcium chloride in a desiccator. The compounds formed were filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol, dried in air, analysed and m.p. noted.

Results including magnetic data after diamagnetic corrections are stated in Table I.

TABLE I

Analyses and physical properties of the complexes.

Complex	Colour	m.p. ⁺ °C	Analyses				Magnetic moment <i>μ</i> _{eff} in B.M.
			% Metal Found	% Metal Reqd	% Nitrogen Found	% Nitrogen Reqd	
1. Cu(II)R ^I ₂	Deep chocolate	166	11.71	11.98	10.38	10.56	1.94
2. Cu(II)R ^{II} ₂	Deep green	178	13.21	13.52	11.60	11.90	1.80
3. Ni(II)R ^I ₂ (P _y) ₂	Greenish yellow	200	8.86	8.64	12.10	12.30	3.16
4. Ni(II)R ^{II} ₂ (P _y) ₂	Chocolate red	270	9.80	9.43	13.33	13.48	3.16
5. Ni(II)R ^{II} ₂	Brown	272	12.75	12.68	12.17	12.04	Dia
6. Co(II)R ^I ₂ (P _y) ₂	Orange	185	8.54	8.65	12.47	12.30	4.89
7. Co(II)R ^I ₂	Yellowish orange	245(d*)	11.05	11.22	11.02	10.67	4.83
8. Co(III)R ^I ₃	Chocolate brown	75	7.65	7.77	11.43	11.08	Dia
9. Co(III)R ^{II} ₃	Black	188	9.02	8.83	13.03	12.58	Dia

*d → decomposition point; + m.p.s. recorded are uncorrected.

Electronic absorption spectra of the compounds were recorded in speck pure ethanolic solutions with the help of a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer. Data are stated in Table II.

TABLE II

Electronic absorption spectral data.

Solvent : Ethanol; in the case of $\text{Co(II)R}_2(\text{P}_y)_2$ small amount of pyridine was added.

Compound	Wave length nm	log ϵ	Compound	Wave length nm	log ϵ	
R ^I H	355	4.296	Ni(II)R ^I ₂ (P _y) ₂	980	1.923	
	235	4.107		800	1.632	
R ^{II} H	362	4.248		650	1.482	
	247	4.125		365	4.701	
Cu(II)R ^I ₂	900	1.298		Ni(II)R ^{II} ₂ (P _y) ₂	245	4.417
	670	1.702			960	1.863
	357	4.579	740		0.900	
	240	4.423	640		0.340	
Cu(II)R ^{II} ₂	900	1.604	Ni(II)R ^{II} ₂	365	4.563	
	670	2.222		245	4.374	
	363	4.605		540	0.889	
	245	4.510		365	4.609	
Co(III)R ^I ₃	470	3.060	Co(II)R ^I ₂ (P _y) ₂	245	4.384	
	360	4.836		940	1.980	
	240	4.636		880	1.898	
Co(III)R ^{II} ₃	470	3.635	Co(II)R ^I ₂	575	1.000	
	370	4.181		370	4.605	
	285	4.665		970	2.195	
	240	4.478		880	2.138	
				600	1.507	
			365	4.601		
			245	4.352		

$\epsilon \rightarrow$ molar extinction co-efficient.

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